

Impact Factor : 7.705

ISSN : 2395 - 5104

शब्दार्णव **Shabdarnav**

International Peer Reviewed Refereed Journal of Multidisciplinary Research

Year-11

Vol.-22, Part-I

July-December, 2025

Scientific Research
Educational Research
Technological Research
Literary Research
Behavioral Research

Editor in Chief

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Published by

SAMNVAY FOUNDATION

Mujaffarpur, Bihar

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Bhartṛhari's concept of kriyā in Vākyapadīyam

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Abstract: The paper explores the concept of kriyā as in Kriyā- samuddeśa in the text Vākyapadīyam of Bhartṛhari. While Pāṇini is often known for his seminal work Aṣṭādhyāyī which offers a precise, highly technical, and structural analysis of kriyā, Bhartṛhari stands no less in this matter in providing a holistic and philosophical understanding; situating kriyā within a metaphysical framework. This paper analyses the Bhartṛhari's exposition of kriyā which includes and surpasses Pāṇini's, as it transcends the limitations that the latter's formal grammatical system by integrating linguistic action with epistemology, metaphysics, and the concept of ultimate reality (Śabda-brahman). It analyses how Kriyā expands its scope into the field of action, thus synthesizing the language, thought and reality.

Keywords: Action, Bhartṛhari, Grammar, Kriyā, Linguistics, Pāṇini, Vākyārtha.

Introduction: Indian philosophical traditions have dedicated themselves to the queries pertaining to the field of language, even before it was identified and called as a system. Study of language as linguistics or philosophy of language are as ancient as the Vedas. It can be said that philosophy of language as a system in India developed with the study and research of the Vedas- the collection of mantras it consists of. The study lied on the assumption that there is a connection between the world and the words of the Vedas.¹

Whether it is Brahmanical school or Śramanical school both have developed their ways in understanding of the relation between words and reality, thought, meaning of words and sentences, etc. Amongst the various topics discussed in both schools, the concept of Kriyā holds an important place, how it influences language and how reality, consciousness, and existence are understood. In Indian philosophy, Kriyā is often closely linked to concepts such as karma (action) and prakṛti (nature). Action is seen as a manifestation of the dynamic interplay between the eternal and transient, the conscious and the material. Whether it is the metaphysical action of the cosmos or the moral actions of human beings, Kriyā is an expression of change, energy, and transformation within the universe. The study of Kriyā thus becomes a means of understanding both the world of phenomena and the underlying reality that sustains it. Kriyā, as the term for 'action' or 'doing', connects directly to how meaning is generated in language and how it reflects the nature of the world we perceive.

In linguistic terms, Kriyā is the primary means by which meaning is communicated. In most languages, verbs are the central building blocks of communication. This idea of Kriyā also plays a significant role in Indian linguistic traditions, as the verb denotes more than just an action in a grammatical sense—it symbolizes a dynamic process in the realm of thought and expression. The verb links the agent (subject) with the act and the object, creating a temporal relationship that conveys not just the structure of a sentence but the unfolding of an event or action in the world.

Pāṇini, one of the most revered figures in the history of linguistics, laid the foundations of Sanskrit grammar in his seminal work, the Aṣṭādhyāyī. Pāṇini's treatment of Kriyā is systematic, technical, and focuses on its grammatical and syntactic role. For Pāṇini, kriyā is primarily realized through verbs, which, according to his rules, are conjugated to express different tenses (kāla), moods (lakāra), and voices. His work essentially classifies Kriyā in terms of how verbs function within the sentence structure—how they agree with subjects, objects, and other elements to create a grammatically correct statement.

What makes Pāṇini's approach unique is his focus on precision and universality. Through his comprehensive rules, Pāṇini creates a framework that applies not just to a single sentence or language but to the entire linguistic system of Sanskrit. In Pāṇini's view, language operates through a set of rules that govern the relationship between words, and Kriyā serves as a vital link in the syntactical structure of a sentence. While this is an indispensable contribution to linguistics, Pāṇini's treatment of Kriyā does not venture into the philosophical or metaphysical dimensions of action. For Pāṇini, Kriyā is primarily a grammatical category, confined to its formal role in constructing meaning.

Bhartṛhari, a grammarian and philosopher who came after Pāṇini, expanded on the concept of Kriyā in a way that transcends grammatical structure. In his work Vākyapadīyam, Bhartṛhari approached Kriyā not merely as a syntactical tool but as an expression of a deeper philosophical truth. His theory is integrally tied to his belief in the holistic nature of language and its connection to the ultimate reality—śabda-brahman, or the eternal, unchanging Word.

Bhartṛhari argued that language and meaning are not just mechanical constructions; they are imbued with a metaphysical significance. According to him, every action (Kriyā) in language is connected to the ultimate truth, the sphaṭa—the indivisible burst of meaning that arises from the interaction between words and their deeper significance. For Bhartṛhari, the verb (as Kriyā) is more than a grammatical component; it is the expression of time, change, and the essence of action in the world.

Bhartṛhari's theory goes beyond the mechanical rules of Pāṇini's grammar and addresses the ontological implications of action. While Pāṇini's focus is on the functional role of verbs in sentences, Bhartṛhari sees verbs as reflecting the changing nature of the cosmos and human experience. Kriyā, for him, symbolizes the relationship between the temporal world of phenomena and the eternal śabda-brahman. Thus, every act of speech or action is not just a mere linguistic utterance but a reflection of the cosmic order, bridging the finite and infinite. His theory introduces a metaphysical dimension to Kriyā, asserting that the verb connects language to the very fabric of reality.

This paper would analyze Bhartṛhari's concept of Kriyā as in his treatise Vākyapadīyam outlining the scheme how Kriyā acts a connector or synthesizes between thought, language and reality.

Bhartṛhari's Concept of Kriyā - All schools of vedic philosophy aim at finding the fundamental principle underlying the creation. While most of the vedic schools identify the principle as brahman, Bhartṛhari identifies the brahman with śabda and the śabda with sphaṭa. The very opening verse in Brahma-kāṇḍa of the treatise Vākyapadīyam summarizes the whole theory. It states thus:

**anādinidhanaṃ brahma śabdatattvaṃ yadaḥśaram |
vivartate'rthabhāvena prakriyā jagato yataḥ (VP 1.1)**

Bhartṛhari identified śabda with Brahman, the metaphysical ultimate reality. Like Brahman, śabda is eternal and indivisible. It has the capacity of differentiation which leads to creation. This power is often referred to as maya- as illusion or as creative power by various systems which modifies (pariṇāma) or makes the Reality appear (vivarta) in different forms. For Bhartṛhari, this creative power is śabda. (VP 1.14) "Even though Bhartṛhari's vivarta is close to pariṇāma, in the sense that it is not an illusory transformation, nevertheless it is not real change either. The differentiation of forms or the process of activity in time is regarded by him as appearances only."²

He believed that language is not just a tool for communication but the very essence of existence. The universe originates from śabda, is sustained by it, and ultimately dissolves into it. The brahman has a conscious desire of differentiation. The expression of this desire occurs as communication. "This capacity of self-expression and communication gives it the character of the word"³ or no less can be called as speech. This association of śabda with the creative power of divine, thus forming connection between the world of differentiation with the ultimate reality.

Unlike the Western notion of language as secondary to reality, he argues that language is ontologically primary. Reality is perceived and experienced through the medium of language. In his philosophy, śabda is not just descriptive but creative. It is the driving force behind the manifestation through the primordial sound, Om. The ultimate reality is inherently linguistic. The manifestation which we perceive is shaped by the categories and structures of language. Thus, language is not external to reality but is its very essence.

Bhartṛhari argued that thought and language are inseparable, asserting that consciousness is fundamentally linguistic in nature. For him, all cognition is shaped by and mediated through language, which makes śabda central to understanding reality. All our mental activity is structured by language. Even before speech is articulated, thoughts take form in linguistic terms. This challenges the common assumption that language merely expresses pre-formed thoughts. The act of speech involves four levels which outlines the relationship between thought, language and external expression. These are as follows:

- Parā- vāk: The transcendental, unmanifest form of speech, residing in śabda-brahma.
- Paśyanti- vāk: The intuitive, ideational stage where thought takes an indistinct, ideational stage where thought takes indistinct linguistic shape.
- Madhyamā- vāk: the intermediate, mental stage where thought is structured into linguistic forms.
- Vaikhāri- vāk: The externalized, articulated form of speech.

Śabda is not a static Reality. Its dynamism is seen its manifestation as Kriyā. Kriyā is the expression of the active and creative Śabda. It is through Kriyā that śabda expresses itself in the phenomenal world. The transformation of thought in the levels of parā- vāk and paśyanti- vāk into spoken language, i.e., vaikhāri-vāk, is mediated by Kriyā. Just as language gives rise to meaning (artha) through speech or thought, it also

manifests as the actions that form the structure and functioning of the cosmos. The act of speaking is in itself a Kriyā where latent thoughts manifest in articulated speech, which further influences actions in the world and how we perceive it. We experience the world through linguistic categories. For instance, the act of naming defines and organizes reality making it intelligible. Bharṭṛhari suggests that without language the reality would remain incomprehensible and formless.

The inherent dynamism and activity of śabda, known as Kriyā, prevades all aspects of existence. It is the process of creation at both transcendental and empirical level. It is the activity that occurs or had occurred in an order or sequence - siddha (in past) and asiddha (in present and future), and is represented by a verb.

**yāvat siddhamasiddham vā sādhyatvenābhidhīyate |
āśritakramarūpatvāt tat kriyetyabhidhīyate. (VP. 3.8.1)**

But Kriyā is not just mere composition of various parts or temporal sequences. These parts are mentally unified to serve a single purpose. Each part that has contributed or will be contributing to the completion of the activity are all equally relevant as they were or are pre-conceived before the initiation of the process.

**samūhaḥ sa tathābhūtaḥ pratibhedam samūhiṣu |
samāpyate tato bhede kālabhedasya sambhavaḥ (VP. 3.8.5)**

Thus, Cognition precedes action. The intention guides Kriyā and the resulting outcomes loop back into cognition. The world as we see know is shaped by our thought with help of Kriyā.

So, to sum up the schema, firstly, there is an intention or desire in the speaker's mind in a unified form as a single mental structure or idea- Sphoṭa. The speaker, through the act of Kriyā, gives this unity outward expression by articulating a sequence of words, one after the other. Even though these words are produced sequentially and might seem distinct from each other in time and space, they all are part of the same Sphoṭa and serve to manifest the same underlying intention or meaning. Thus, Kriyā represents the dynamic unfolding of this internal unity of Sphoṭa into the external form of language. In this sense, Kriyā is the action through which the speaker's unified intention is communicated to the listener, who then re-captures that same Sphoṭa in their mind. The listener, through their own mental process of comprehension, also engages in Kriyā as they reconstruct the meaning from the series of word-sounds. Though the words come sequentially, the listener grasps the meaning of the sentence as a single unified entity. Therefore, we can see Kriyā acts as a mediator between thought, language and reality.

Conclusion - Language, thought and reality may have been treated ontologically by many schools- Indian and Western. While we find celebrated theories of the West like Russel's logical atomism, Wittgenstein's picture theory or Austin's performative theory explaining the relation between the three, such theories were discussed in Indian philosophical system much earlier than the former schools. In Indian system, Mimāṃsā, Nyāya or Buddhism- they all have discussed about language thought and reality, however, Bharṭṛhari's concept is unique in the sense that there is primacy of language in his philosophy, where language is equated to reality and the relationship amongst language, thought and reality is explained through Kriyā.

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